

THE EUROPEAN UNION'S INSTITUTIONS AND THE ECONOMIC RELATIONSHIPS WITH ISRAEL

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Abstract: *The European Union and Israel have a long-shared history, characterized by mutual dependence and increasing cooperation - both share the same values of democracy, respect for freedom and the rule of law, and both are committed to an open international economic system based on market principles. Israeli leaders in the fields of politics, industry, commerce and science are in close contact with Europe. Over five decades of trade, cultural exchange, political cooperation and a developed system of agreements have created these relations. This article will try to present the EU's economic institutions and show the system of mutual relations with the State of Israel.*

Key words: *European union; Economic relations; Political cooperation.*

INSTITUȚIILE UNIUNII EUROPENE ȘI RELAȚIILE ECONOMICE CU ISRAEL

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Rezumat: *Uniunea Europeană și Israelul au o istorie comună de lungă durată, caracterizată prin dependență reciprocă și cooperare crescândă - ambele împărtășesc aceleași valori de democrație, respect pentru libertate și statul de drept și ambele sunt angajați într-un sistem economic internațional deschis bazat pe pe principiile pieței. Liderii israelieni din domeniile politicii, industriei, comerțului și științei sunt în strânsă legătură cu Europa. Peste cinci decenii de comerț, schimburi culturale, cooperare politică și un sistem dezvoltat de acorduri au creat aceste relații. Acest articol va încerca să prezinte instituțiile economice ale UE și să arate sistemul de relații reciproce cu statul Israel.*

Cuvinte cheie: *Uniunea Europeană; relații economice; cooperare politică.*

The European Union and Israel have a long-shared history, characterized by mutual dependence and increasing cooperation - both share the same values of democracy, respect for freedom and the rule of law, and both are committed to an

open international economic system based on market principles. Israeli leaders in the fields of politics, industry, commerce and science are in close contact with Europe. Over five decades of trade, cultural exchange, political cooperation and a developed system of agreements have created these relations. The organizations of the European Union are based on the existence of institutions that faithfully represent the various ideologies, as well as the relationship with the State of Israel. The European Union has several central institutions entrusted with decision-making, their implementation and control over them:

1. **Council of the European union** - The institution that represents the governments of the member states, is the EU's main decision-making body. The ministers representing the EU member meet as part of the Council, and the representative of each state is the minister relevant to the matter in question. Each member states holds the presidency of the council in turn, and the president rotates every six months. Its activities are in the field of legislation. The Council coordinates guidelines for the member states' broad economic policy, makes decisions on shared foreign and security policy and decides on measures in the field of legal and police cooperation in matters of crime. Together with the European Parliament, the Council is the body that approves the EU's annual budget.
2. **The European Parliament** - The European Parliament currently has 705 members sent from the 27 EU member states (the number of members each country sends is determined by the relative size of its population). The Parliament is one of the three main EU institutions, along with the European Commission and the Council, and is the only one of the three whose representatives are directly elected by the member countries' citizens. The European Parliament has roles in three areas, as detailed below:
 - 1.1 **Approval of legislation:** Parliament's approval is required for bills in most areas (in some areas approval by the Council is sufficient).
 - 1.2 **Approval of budget:** The Parliament approves the budget in cooperation with the Council of the European union. In some sections (such as foreign aid) the parliament is the determining factor and in other sections (such as agriculture) it is the Council of the European union that determines. Parliament has veto power over the budget.
 - 1.3 **Supervision:** Parliament approves or rejects candidates to serve as heads of the commission; It must vote confidence in the commission

prior to it taking office, and has the authority to demand that the commission resign - but to date this authority has not been used

3. **The European Central Bank** - The European Central Bank is solely responsible for the member monetary policy of the Eurozone member states (the states that have adopted the single currency). The bank works with the central national banks of these countries, in what is known as the "European system of central banks". The central national banks are responsible for printing the euro and distributing it throughout the Eurozone, and the heads of these banks sit on the council responsible for the European Central Bank, along with five permanent representatives.

The connection with the State of Israel. In the framework of the Euro-Mediterranean partnership and with the aim of advancing it, a framework agreement was signed in June 2000 between the European Investment Bank and Israel, according to which the bank will be able to finance projects in Israel. It should be noted that even before signing this agreement, the bank invested in Israel within the framework of various economic agreements. From 1978 until August 2020, the European Bank invested approximately 980 million Euros in Israel, in projects whose main aim is to promote economic development in Israel, emphasizing the promotion of the private sector. According to the bank's data, about 250 small to medium industrial projects were financed with loans on its behalf.

The document that shapes the legal framework of bilateral relations between Israel and the EU is the association agreement signed in 1995 and ratified in 2000 both in the Knesset and in the Parliaments of the 15 EU countries at the time. **According to the agreement, there will be a continuous dialogue between Israel and the EU within the framework of two bodies: the Association Committee and the Association Council.** The first is at the level of representatives of the agreement and the second at the level of ministers. **This agreement brought to light Israel's membership in the Euro-Mediterranean Partnership, also known as the "Barcelona Process".** This partnership, which was founded following the Barcelona Declaration of November 28, 1995, seeks to promote these three goals:

- A. Defining a common area of peace and stability with the help of ongoing political and security dialogue.
- B. Creating economic cooperation between the partnership and the gradual creation of a free trade area between the countries of the Middle East and the EU.

C. Establishing closer relations between the nations with the help of social and cultural partnership between Israel and the member states.

The cooperation between Israel and the EU in the field of science takes place in several fields. Israel was the first country outside Europe to be included in the "European Community framework programs for research and technical development", three-year programs designed to create a European research area - an internal market of information and knowledge. Israel was added to the Fourth Framework Program in August 1996 and since then has signed two additional agreements included it in the Fifth Framework Programs 1999-2002, and the Sixth Framework Program 2003-2006. As part of these agreements, Israel contributes to the budget of the programs and receives all the participation benefits that European countries receive.

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